

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN MODERN EDUCATION

¹Akbar Shonazarov, ²Sarvarbek Melikuziyev

^{1,2}“Tashkent institute of irrigation and agricultural mechanization engineers” National research university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11221639>

Abstract. *The role and the effective usage of innovative technologies in teaching are considered in this article. The Internet links, which are effectively used during the lessons, are also shown here.*

Keywords: *education, information, technology, teaching method, training*

Introduction. Today, our country dictates new tasks of social modernization, industrialization and accelerated innovation challenges in the new global economic integration. The main objective of the third decade of the XXI century of independent Uzbekistan is to move forward to joining the top 30 developed countries of the world. In this regard, there is a great responsibility on educated and highly qualified young people of Kazakhstan, such as the development of national competitiveness in the century, providing prosperity and universal recognition of the country all over the world. The role of innovation in education is great. The effective use of Innovative technologies, such as computers, the Internet, multimedia resources in the educational process is the only way to show the quality of education. One of the innovative technologies of improving the students’ communicative abilities is using multimedia in the process of teaching and learning in the classroom. Proper use of multimedia in classroom will provide the opportunity for interacting with diverse texts that give students a solid background in the tasks and content of mainstream courses.

Analysis And Solution. Furthermore, because educational technology is expected to become an integral part of the curriculum, students must become proficient in accessing and using electronic resources. In terms of providing educational institutions with multimedia products, there are some problems to be solved so far:

-the virtual absence of domestic electronic textbooks (ET) in official language at educational institutions;

-lack of effectiveness of using the existing electronic textbooks;

-poor quality of teacher training in using electronic textbooks;

-insufficient implementation of new educational technologies in the educational process;

-low efficiency of automated assessment system in teaching.

Learners obtain most of the information from electronic devices, which has made such tools, a very essential component of their daily life [1].

So, why do I use multimedia materials in the classroom? First, it helps to enhance understanding. Valuable media materials boost student comprehension of complex topics, especially dynamic processes that unfold over time. At second, it increases memorability –rich media materials lead to better encoding and easier retrieval.

Result. The most important advantage is that media helps to improve their four language skills like listening, reading, speaking and writing. Moreover, information technology develops students’ critical thinking. Furthermore, multimedia provides us with individualized learning, which means that multimedia resources can help you meet needs of many different types of

learners. Like, Visual learners can watch a video, while auditory learners listen to streaming audio hands-on learners play and interactive game. Students who need extra practice can use online exercises to improve their grammar or vocabulary skills. Modeling of real authentic environment by attracting Internet -resources is not only a successful development of the language, but also allows you to understand the fundamental laws of the unity and diversity of culture. In additionally, we want to share with useful teaching Internet links for ELT:

- English Tutor Bournemouth The website provides free resources for teachers and students on a range of GCSE and 'A' Level texts. Key quotations, annotated poetry, character profiles, worksheets etc. The site has a second purpose, which is to offer private tutoring services;

-book Box from Channel Learning Features interviews with leading children's authors, poets, illustrators. Suggestions for reading with reviews and excerpts. Templates for pitching the film of the book;

- BBEC ENG DEPT An ever- growing collection of links for teachers of English and their students;

-easy Read Shakespeare Easy Read Shakespeare is a new version of Shakespeare's plays formatted in a way to make them easier to follow from the printed page. Character portraits are used to help the reader follow the conversations and location drawings help set the scene. A great resource for anyone studying Shakespeare who can't get to see the plays;

-hope Education Broad range of English teaching materials including books, speaking and listening tools, phonics and story packs;

-literary Connections links, books and resources for secondary English -mainly but not exclusively for literature;

-teacher's Pet Text Tool for Teachers is a free add-on for Microsoft Word that can help you transform any text into a fun classroom activity. Developed by a teacher, here are just some of the things the tool can do: Crosswords Flashcards Bingo Cards Jumbles Gap-fill.

Conclusions

Thus, the innovative technologies that we reviewed today significantly enrich and diversify the teaching of foreign languages. In place of the monotonous work comes intelligent creative search, during which formed a new type of personality, active and purposeful, focused on constant self-education and development. Multimedia technology could significantly enhance student's capability in problem solving and in learning by doing.

REFERENCES

1. G. Shadmanova, S.S. Mirzaev, Modern information and communication technologies. TIAME, Tashkent, 2018
2. McCarthy B. "Integration: the sine qua non of CALL", CALL-EJ online 1, 2, September 2009.
3. Davies G. "Lessons from the past, lessons for the future: 20 years of CALL". 22.11.2016.